

Accepted version, archived after the expiry of the embargo period
Published in Ratio, 2019, 32:2 (104—113)
Link to published version: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/rati.12227>

Original Article

The weight of facts: a puzzle about perception, reasons and deliberation

Andrea Giananti

Department of Philosophy, University of Fribourg, Avenue de l'Europe 20, Fribourg 1700, Switzerland.

Correspondence

Andrea Giananti, Department of Philosophy, University of Fribourg, Avenue de l'Europe 20, Fribourg 1700, Switzerland.

Email: andrea.giananti@unifr.ch

Abstract

How should we understand the epistemic role of perception? According to *epistemological disjunctivism* (ED), a subject's perceptual knowledge that *p* is to be explained in terms of the subject believing that *p* for a factive and reflectively accessible reason. I argue that ED raises far-reaching questions for rationality and deliberation; I illustrate those questions by setting up a puzzle about belief-suspension, and I argue that ED does not have the resources to make sense of the rationality of belief-suspension in cases in which suspending is clearly rational. The conclusion that I draw from the puzzle is mainly negative: the epistemic contribution of perception cannot be explained in terms of a warrant-conferring relation between perception and *belief*. However, toward the end, I sketch a positive picture of the epistemic role of perception in terms of a direct explanatory relation between perception and *knowledge*.

KEYWORDS: belief-suspension, deliberation, epistemological disjunctivism, perceptual recognition; reasons

Funding information

Research for this article was funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation, grant n. 100012M_173159.

1 | Introduction

According to *epistemological disjunctivism* (ED) (McDowell, 1994, 2002, 2006, 2011; Pritchard, 2012), if a subject perceptually knows that *p*, that is because she is in possession of a reason for her belief that *p* that is both *factive* and *reflectively accessible* to her. That the reason is factive means that it entails that the believed proposition is true; the notion of reflective access is more complicated, but let us simply say that a reflectively accessible reason is such that the subject can access it simply on the basis of introspection.

According to Pritchard and McDowell, the reason that combines factivity and reflective access in the case of vision is *seeing that*: thus, ED comes down to explaining a subject's visual knowledge

that p in terms of the subject believing that p for the reason that she sees that p;¹ in this paper I am concerned with vision – henceforth, I will simply talk of perception and perceptual knowledge to refer to visual experience and visual knowledge.

Most of the recent work on ED has focussed on the *entailment thesis* (ET), namely the thesis that seeing that p entails knowing that p, and the so-called *basis problem* (Pritchard 2012), namely that if ET is true, it is difficult to understand how *seeing that* can be a basis for knowledge. However, it is striking that a lot of energy has been spent on evaluating the *linguistic* evidence against or in favour of ET (especially French, 2012; Pritchard, 2012; Turri, 2010), while the question of what it means for perception to be the basis of knowledge has largely remained neglected. Furthermore, although the relevant linguistic issues are certainly interesting, the relationship between *seeing that* and *knowing that* raises general questions about rationality, theoretical deliberation and belief-suspension which have not been adequately addressed in the literature so far.²

In the second section, I develop an understanding of the basis problem. This will set the stage for the third section, where I argue that real trouble for ED comes into view when we analyse the implications of ED for epistemic rationality: it is a simple puzzle about belief-suspension, I contend, that is fatal to ED. In the fourth section, I consider and reject two attempts to defend ED. Finally, I sketch an alternative picture of the relationship between perception and knowledge – one which envisages a direct connection between perception and *knowledge*, without an explanatory detour via belief.

2 | THE ENTAILMENT THESIS AND THE BASIS PROBLEM

It is often held that seeing that p is just a way of knowing that p (Cassam, 2007; Dretske, 1969; Stroud, 2009; Williamson, 2000). But, in much of the discussion surrounding ED, it is a logically weaker thesis that has received most attention, namely the *entailment thesis* (ET):

Entailment thesis (ET): seeing that p entails knowing that p.

Pritchard worries that if ET is true, then it is ‘hard to see how...[seeing that p] can be part of the rational basis for one’s paradigmatic perceptual knowledge’ (2012, p. 25), and he calls this the *basis problem*. Although I agree with Pritchard that ET spells trouble for ED, Pritchard does not offer any explanation as to why the truth of ET would make it hard to understand how seeing that p can be the basis for one’s knowledge. Some interpretative work is required to figure out what is going on.

On the interpretation that I would like to offer, the basis problem has deep roots in a conception according to which knowing and believing are active, free exercises of reason, whereas perceiving is an event in which the subject is passive. Thus, it should not be the case that the mere occurrence of an event in which the subject is passive determines whether or not the subject knows or believes something. A good starting point for approaching this conception is a well-known passage in McDowell’s *Mind and World*:

In a particular experience in which one is not misled, what one takes in is *that things are thus and so*. *That things are thus and so* is the content of the experience, and it can also be the content of a judgement: it becomes the content of a judgement if the subject decides to take the experience at face value [...] *that things are thus and so* is also...an aspect of the layout of the world. (1994, p. 26)

¹ I’ll set aside McDowell’s oscillations between saying that the reason is the fact that p (see his 2002, p. 280) and that the reason is the fact that one sees that p (see his 2006, p. 134); my argument can be run on either version.

² Although see Ginsborg (2006) and Roessler (2009) for illuminating discussions of the topic of perception and reason from a perspective similar to that which I adopt here.

According to McDowell, perceptually taking in ‘an aspect of the layout of the world’ is not sufficient for knowledge: for the experiencing subject to have knowledge, it must also be the case that she *decides* to endorse in judgement what was taken in in perception, for only thus does she freely exercise her reason. This sets disjunctivism apart from an externalistically-minded view on which the epistemic role of perception would be to reliably cause accurate beliefs. While disjunctivists maintain that there is an objective connection between justification and truth, they also insist that the epistemic import of perception is not to be thought of as a rigid causal mechanism, but rather as something that engages one’s rationality.

So that we can easily refer back to it, let us label the point that it must be possible for the subject to perceptually take in an aspect of the world by having an experience with the content that things are thus and so, while exercising her reason by not taking that at face value:

Rational suspension: it must be possible that there are cases in which it is rational for a subject to be in the following complex state: S sees that p and S does not believe that p.

The cognitive performance which consists in accepting or rejecting the content of the experience belongs to a family of activities examples of which are reflecting on one’s evidence and assessing the strength of reasons. McDowell talks of activities of this kind as an engagement in rational *scrutiny*. Of the relations between the contents of perception and candidate contents of belief, he says:

If these relations are to be genuinely recognizable as reason-constituting [...] [t]he relations themselves must be able to come under the self-scrutiny of active thinking. (1994, p. 53)

Let us label the requirement that the relations between perception and belief be scrutinizable:

Scrutiny: it must be possible for a subject to scrutinize putative perceptual reasons for belief.

Rational suspension and *Scrutiny* are closely associated: for a process of rational scrutiny to have any substance, it has to be at least *possible* that the subject will find the putative perceptual reason insufficient; a process of scrutiny in which, as a matter of principle, what is scrutinized always passes the test, is not a scrutiny at all. But now the problem for ED is that, on the relatively uncontroversial assumption that knowledge entails belief, ET is incompatible with both *Rational suspension* and *Scrutiny*. This can be easily understood: if *seeing that* entails *believing that*, it can never be the case that the first conjunct in *Rational suspension* obtains while the second doesn’t; furthermore, if the entailment obtains, then in seeing that things are a certain way the subject has already made up her mind as to what to believe, so the activity of rational scrutiny does never get started.

We finally have an adequate understanding of the basis problem: perception exerts a rational pressure on an experiencing subject by disclosing aspects of the layout of reality to her; but for perception to be a basis for knowledge, it has to be possible for the subject to evaluate and in principle even reject the deliverances of perception; but if *seeing that* entails *knowing that*, that kind of rational evaluation is not possible.

In the next section, I present the disjunctivist solution to the basis problem and I argue that ED fails by its own lights: given how ED conceives of perceptual reasons, perceptual reasons are impervious to the relevant kind of rational scrutiny; furthermore, ED fails even if ET is false.

3 | THE WEIGHT OF FACTS

Pritchard and McDowell offer a simple solution to the basis problem: they reject ET. Pritchard says that *seeing that* ‘guarantees that one is in a good position to gain knowledge’ (2012, p. 26); however, it doesn’t entail belief, and *a fortiori* not knowledge. Likewise, McDowell conceives of perception as ‘something in which there is no attitude of acceptance or endorsement at all, but only...an invitation to adopt such an attitude.’ (2002, p. 278)

Let us review Pritchard’s argument against ET. Pritchard asks us to imagine a modified fake-barn case: you are looking at a barn in perfectly good conditions, but you are falsely told by an otherwise reliable informant that you are in barn-façade county, so you refrain from believing that there is a barn in front of you. Imagine that, at a later time, you discover that the testimony was false. How would you reappraise your earlier perceptual experience in light of this discovery? Pritchard writes:

...suppose that one were to discover subsequently that the testimony one received was false...Wouldn’t one now retrospectively treat oneself as having earlier seen that there was a barn?...Wouldn’t it be most natural to say that one did see that there was a barn in the field, rather than to ‘hedge’ one’s assertion by saying, for example, that one merely thought that one saw a barn? But if that’s right, then it does appear that there is good reason for supposing that one does see that there is a barn in this case, even though one can’t know the target proposition. (2012, pp. 26—27)

I will suppose for dialectical purposes that Pritchard’s description of the situation is adequate, and that it gives us some *prima facie* reason to doubt ET.³ I will also assume that belief-suspension when you receive the testimony is rational. What I want to investigate is whether belief-suspension can be seen to be rational given disjunctivist presuppositions. Here I set up a puzzle in metaphorical terms, and in the next section I elaborate on it in more technical terms.

When the question arises of what you ought to believe, you can take your epistemic scale and weigh up the evidence on its plates; then you check whether there is a side which clearly outweighs the other and you form your attitudes accordingly. Let us suppose that you see that there is a barn in the envisaged case. So you weigh up the fact that you see that there is a barn on one plate of the scale, and the false information that you are in barn-façade county on the other. If you rationally suspend belief, that means that the false information prevails. But there is something absurd about this: you cannot put the fact that you see that *p* on your epistemic scale without thereby settling the issue whether you ought to believe that *p*; because *seeing that* is manifestly factive, whatever else is being weighed up on the other plate is irrelevant – a linguistic reflection of this is that asserting things of the form ‘I see that *p* but I don’t believe that *p*’ is clearly irrational. In the next paragraphs I point out two important implications for ED and then I draw a general moral.

The first implication of the puzzle is that disjunctivists fail by their own lights: they place requirements on reasons, such as *Rational suspension* and *Scrutiny*, which reasons as conceived of by ED cannot possibly satisfy. McDowell conceives of perceptual reasons as something the epistemic significance of which must be open to scrutiny by the experiencing subject. But if reasons for perceptual beliefs are provided by manifestly factive states such as *seeing that*, there is actually nothing to scrutinize: the only rational thing to do in light of those reasons is to adjust one’s own attitudes to match the facts – someone who was intent on actually scrutinizing *seeing that p* with respect to the question whether she ought to believe that *p* would be someone who would potentially say things like ‘I see that *p* but I wonder whether I ought to believe that *p*’, and that is not a rational thing to say.

The second implication is one which we can only appreciate because we have approached our topic from the angle of epistemic rationality, not linguistics: dropping ET does not help the disjunctivist to get out of the predicament at all. For suppose that McDowell and Pritchard are right that *seeing that* does not entail knowledge. Even if this were true, the problem is that *seeing that* is

³ McDowell’s argument in his (2002, p. 277) resembles Pritchard’s.

required to do work which it cannot do: on the one hand, it provides a reason for belief as strong as it could possibly be; on the other, it is supposed that we must be able to reflect on such reason and possibly set it aside, and this seems inconsistent – the problem of squaring the manifest factivity of *seeing that* with conditions on a meaningful deliberative process is left untouched by the rejection of ET.

This is the puzzle of the weight of facts: on the one hand, once the fact that there is a barn is perceptually available, that is too weighty a consideration to be counterbalanced by anything; on the other hand, it seems that the testimonial evidence that the environment is abnormal makes it perfectly rational for you to suspend the belief that there is a barn. What makes the puzzle intractable is that rationality pulls you into two different directions at the same time: because it is unintelligible how seeing that *p* could be part of the evidential basis for a rational suspension of the belief that *p*, it seems that the only rational thing to do is to believe that *p*; but, at the same time, it seems perfectly rational to rely on the testimony of a highly reliable informant. How could a phenomenon as simple as trusting an informant have become such a mess? The attempt to explain perceptual knowledge in terms of a belief for which perception provides a factive and reflectively accessible warrant has led us into a muddle.

In what follows, I consider two escape-routes for disjunctivists and I argue that neither is viable.

4 | INDEFEASIBLE REASONS DEFEATED?

The two reactions that I want to explore are each a possible development of a comment that Pritchard makes in passing: that the false testimony in the modified fake-barn case is a ‘misleading defeater’ (2012, p. 27).⁴ So the first thing to do to get a better grip on what kind of role the false testimony is supposed to play is to understand what are defeaters and how defeat works.

We can construe defeaters as pieces of evidence. Suppose that, given a piece of evidence, *e*, it is rational to believe a hypothesis *h*. A defeater is a piece of evidence, *d*, such that it downgrades the epistemic status of the belief in *h*, because the conjunction of *e* and *d*, unlike *e* alone, does not make it rational to believe that *h*.⁵ Is it appropriate to cast the false testimony in our modified fake-barn case as a defeater? Before we answer the question, we should distinguish between two kinds of defeaters.⁶

a) Rebutting defeaters

A rebutting defeater of the belief that *p* gives a subject a reason to believe not-*p*. If Charlie tells me that there will be a party at 67, Union Road in my city tonight, but then I discover that there is no Union Road in my city, the newly acquired information is a rebutting defeater, because it gives me a reason to believe that there will not be a party at the aforementioned location.

But on many plausible ways of spelling out the testimony in the modified fake-barn case, the testimony is not a rebutting defeater. Suppose, for example, that the informant tells you that only every second of the things that look like a barn is a real barn. It is clear that that is not a positive reason to believe that the object in front of you is not a barn, but simply a reason to suspend belief, so it is not a rebutting defeater.

b) Undercutting and higher-order defeat

An undercutting defeater of the belief that *p* suggests that the evidential basis on which the subject has formed or would form her belief is inadequate, insofar as the defeater is ‘a reason for supposing that one’s ground for believing *p* is not sufficiently indicative of the truth of the belief’ (Sudduth, section 6a).

⁴ McDowell agrees with Pritchard that if the subject retained her belief that she wouldn’t thereby have knowledge.

⁵ Compare Chisholm (1989, pp. 52–60) and Coates (2012, p. 118).

⁶ The distinction that follows in the main text is due to Pollock (1986).

However, according to ED, the relevant evidential basis is that one sees that *p*, and it is absurd to say that seeing that *p* is not sufficiently indicative of the truth of *p*. So it is obscure how ordinary cases of defeat could apply to *seeing that*.⁷

But perhaps disjunctivists need not throw away the notion of undercutting defeat for their purposes. Things might work better if the testimony is cast as an undercutting defeater of the belief that *I see that p*. Conceived of in this way, the information is a *higher-order defeater* in the sense that it raises doubts concerning what grounds one has for thinking that one *sees* that there is a barn, hence ‘takes away’ one’s reason to believe that there is a barn.

Thinking in terms of higher-order defeat would allow disjunctivists to reformulate the deliberative process in a way that does not leave them in an absurd situation. The starting point of the reformulation would be that there are doxastic conditions on possessing evidence: in order for one to have a piece of evidence one must, at a minimum, believe that one has the evidence. So, for *seeing that there is a barn* to figure in the process, the subject must believe that she sees that there is a barn. But the misleading testimony precisely defeats that belief, so, insofar as the subject is epistemically responsible, *seeing that there is a barn* drops out of the deliberation.

This is more sensible than option (a). However, to make real progress, we need to figure out how exactly the testimony undercuts the belief that one sees that *p*. Below I consider two possibilities, and I argue that neither is satisfactory.

b₁) Factive evidence and the dogmatism paradox

According to McDowell, it is a single exercise of a single capacity that gives one perceptual knowledge that there is a barn and at the same time self-knowledge that one sees that there is a barn:

...perceptual knowledge includes knowledge that it is through perception that one knows whatever it is that one knows about the environment. (2011, pp. 41—42)

On a plausible interpretation of McDowell, seeing that *p* does double duty: it justifies the belief that *p*, and it also justifies the belief that I see that *p*. Now, for ED to work, it must be the case that the testimony can undercut the latter. But if the evidence for believing that I see that *p* is again the fact that I see that *p*, then it is absurd to suggest that that basis is not sufficiently indicative of the fact that I see that *p*.

Let us imagine a temporal succession. At *t*₁, you see that there is a barn and believe on that basis that there is a barn. By exercising the relevant self-conscious capacity, you know at *t*₁ that there is a barn, and that you see that there is a barn. At *t*₂, I give you the false information. At *t*₂, by hypothesis, you still see that there is a barn. Now, suppose that at *t*₂ you cling to your beliefs: you see that there is a barn, and you believe *on that basis* both that there is a barn and that you see that there is a barn. Given that the relevant basis is such as to guarantee that your beliefs are true, why would you be doing anything wrong?

The problem I’m presenting is a particularly thorny version of the so-called *dogmatism paradox*. Very roughly, the paradox is that if I know that *p* on the basis of evidence *e*, any evidence against *p* is misleading. Now, if I’m entitled to discard misleading evidence, it seems that as long as I retain my belief that *p* on the basis of *e*, I know that *p*; but this attitude engenders a seemingly unacceptable amount of dogmatism.⁸ The paradox has predictably suscitated a lot of interest, and a popular solution consists in saying that knowledge is defeasible (e.g., Conee 2004). However,

⁷ McDowell himself says that perceptual states ‘provide *indefeasible* warrant for perceptual beliefs’ (2011, p. 38).

⁸ The paradox was first presented by Kripke at a talk in 1972 at Cambridge University. Harman, who was in the audience, wrote it down in an extremely condensed form: ‘If I know that *h* is true, I know that any evidence against *h* is evidence against something that is true; I know that such evidence is misleading. But I should disregard evidence that I know is misleading. So, once I know that *h* is true, I am in a position to disregard any future evidence that seems to tell against *h*’ (1973: 148).

philosophers articulating this solution typically focus on cases in which one's basis for *p* does not entail *p*. I think that that makes all the difference, thus that strategy is not applicable to the present case.

Suppose that at t_1 you form the belief that there is a barn on the basis that it *looks* to you that there is a barn, and that you thereby come to *know* that there is a barn.⁹ At t_2 , I give you misleading evidence that you are in fake-barn county. Now, it is plausible that if at t_2 you retain your belief on the same basis as t_1 , what you have at t_2 is mere true belief, not knowledge, because the total evidence does not support your belief, which is thus irresponsibly held – I might very well tell you: 'I appreciate that that object looks like a barn, but that is not a sufficient basis in the present circumstances'. But the situation is completely altered if the basis for your belief is that you *see* that there is a barn, because then it doesn't make sense to suggest that the total evidence does not support the relevant proposition – correlatively, it wouldn't make sense for me to tell you: 'I appreciate that you see that there is a barn, but do you really know that there is a barn?'

To sum up: if seeing that *p* can be the basis both for believing that *p* and that I see that *p*, we haven't found a clear rational process by which to defeat the latter.

b₂) Non-factive evidence and scrutiny

An alternative option for ED-theorists would be to extend disjunctivism to 'internal' seemings: in the paradigmatic, good case, *S* knows that she sees that *p* simply by seeing that *p*; but the case under examination is not a good case, so it should be explained differently.

The idea could be elaborated as follows: when you receive the false testimony, it is rational to wonder what is your evidence for believing that you see a barn, and to conclude that in the present circumstances your evidence is simply that you are seeing something that *looks* like a barn; but, given the circumstances, this evidence is not sufficiently indicative of the truth of the relevant proposition. This view resembles traditional, broadly Cartesian forms of internalism, on which the subject has immediately justified beliefs about her own sensory states (such as *its looking to one as though there is a barn*) and then obtains justification for beliefs concerning mind-independent objects by means of general epistemic principles and background beliefs. However, as ED-theorists might point out, the fact that ED resembles Cartesian internalism in the bad case does not mean that ED is committed to the same kind of explanation in the good case.

The problem is that this implies a reformulation of the process of belief-suspension that is not consistent with ED. What is weighed up on the scale is some non-factive evidence such as *its looking as though there is a barn*. Now, if this is what is weighed up, we certainly can make sense of a rational scrutiny that ends with that evidence being outweighed. But this is not how the process was supposed to work, for a subject was supposed to be able to scrutinize the relation between *p* and *seeing that p*, not just between *p* and *its seeming to one that p*. What this brings out is that a proper rational scrutiny can only get started with reasons that do not obviously entail the truth of the candidate content for belief – as far as perceptual reasons are concerned, all that can ever be meaningfully weighed up are relatively weak reasons of the form *its seeming to one that p*.

Crucially, this reflects negatively on the disjunctivist treatment of the *good* case. According to ED, in order for perception to be intelligibly thought of as a basis for knowledge, something like IND and *Scrutiny* must obtain; but it remains unintelligible what form the scrutiny could possibly take when there is no misleading evidence and the subject does not weigh up a mere appearance on her scale. Of course, in principle I could *contemplate* the relation between *p* and seeing that *p* all day: 'I see that *p*; *p*. I see that *p*; *p*...' – but this is precisely not a *scrutiny*, as the possibility of rejecting *p* is excluded in principle, unless I stop being rational or get confused on the meaning of the terms.

⁹ A view on which all episodes of *it seeming to one that p* gives one prima facie justification for *p* has been articulated by Pryor (2000) with the label of *dogmatism*.

The problem of the weight of facts was to make sense of rationally scrutinizing manifestly factive reasons. Pointing out that we can scrutinize and reject weaker, *non-factive* reasons in the bad case does not address the problem at all, and ED-theorists are left without an explanation of why their description of the *good* case is different to an externalistically-minded, merely causal explanation of belief.

The disjunctivist predicament has finally come out here in full generality: disjunctivists want to have factive reasons *and* a rational scrutiny based on those factive reasons, but, as the analysis of the process of scrutiny in the modified fake-barn case has brought out, this does not seem to add up to a coherent view.

I conclude by gesturing toward an alternative construal of *seeing that* and I explain how this could solve the puzzle. Crucially, the solution carries with it a deep revision of the relationship between belief-held-for-a-reason and knowledge.

5 | CONCLUSION: PERCEPTION, RECOGNITION AND KNOWLEDGE

How should we account for the epistemological role of perception? I suggest that answering this question calls for a reversal of the way in which the relation between perception and knowledge has traditionally been thought of. The fundamental point is that the relevant explanatory relation is not between perception and belief-held-for-a-reason, but rather between perception and *knowledge*: perceptual experience puts us in a position to know that *p*, and we can understand the perception-knowledge link without conceiving of perception as a reason for belief. Fleshing out the details of this explanatory relation is far beyond the scope of this paper, but I think that two notions should be given a central role: that of object-perception and that of a recognitional capacity. By consciously presenting us with objects in our environment, perceptual experience puts us in a position to exercise our capacity perceptually to recognize and hence *know* an object to be of a certain kind. More precisely, seeing that an object is some way *consists* in visually recognizing that the perceived object is of a certain kind. Crucially, this also illuminates the rationality of perceptual belief, because that you have recognized the object to be of a certain kind is an excellent reason for you to believe that the object is of the relevant kind.¹⁰

In addition to providing an elegant model for ordinary cases of perceptual knowledge, this model could also help us solve the puzzle. We can conceive of the dialectic between the deliverances of perception on the one hand, and background knowledge, evidence and features of the environment on the other, in terms of the transition from seeing an object to seeing that the object is some way. More specifically, what we need is a description of how the transition from seeing an object to seeing (recognizing) that the object is some way might get stopped in its tracks, as it were.

A recognitional capacity is a *dispositional* trait of an individual, such that one has it just in case one can reliably tell that objects of a certain kind are present by looking at them. Now, it is a well-known fact that the manifestation of a disposition can be hindered in several ways. When applied to perception, this means that there are ways in which the transition from seeing a barn to recognizing it as a barn might be hindered or suspended.

Let us consider again the case in which you are looking at a barn in perfectly good conditions while having misleading evidence that you are in barn-façade county. You certainly do see *a barn*, because no amount of misleading evidence can change the fact that you are in an appropriate sensory relation to it. What blocks the transition is that, because you trust the informant, you *refrain* from applying the relevant recognitional capacity. But since seeing that an object is some way consists in recognizing it to be that way, you don't see that there is a barn, and thus you don't find yourself in the absurd situation of weighing up a fact in theoretical deliberation only to discard it in favour of misleading evidence.

¹⁰ For two different versions of a 'recognition-based' approach to perceptual knowledge and the rationality of perceptual belief, see Millar (2011) and Roessler (2011).

I would like to conclude by noting that construing the dialectic between misleading evidence and reasons in terms of capacities can be helpful in addressing related puzzles that arise outside the perceptual domain. Suppose that you have just proved a theorem, T , but your math teacher warns you that in this area of mathematics many students forget to check whether they are dividing by zero. Proof is factive, but it seems reasonable for you to suspend belief in T (to make this more vivid, we might suppose that you have occasionally been too optimistic about your ‘proofs’ in the past). How should we square the rationality of belief-suspension with the fact that you have an indefeasible reason for believing T ?

The foregoing reflection on capacities suggests a way forward. When you prove something, you exercise certain capacities, such as recognizing inferential patterns and performing arithmetic operations. My suggestion is that when you prove T , you come to *know* T as a result of the exercise of the capacities in questions. But when your teacher puts you on guard, you do something analogous to suspending the exercise of the recognitional capacity in the barn case. More precisely: suppose that the alleged proof requires doing a division, but you can do that only if the divisor is different from zero. After you talk to your teacher, you call into question the right that you have of exercising the capacity to divide numbers in that context. In other words, you put in ‘quarantine’ the result of your previous exercise of that capacity, thus your belief in the whole proof is suspended, with a consequent loss of knowledge.

I hope to have pointed toward a promising route: what we need is a description of different *ways of knowing* or coming to know something (such as *seeing that* and *proving that*) and the specific capacities that they involve. Once these capacities are described, it can also become clear why and in what circumstances their exercise can be hindered, with the result of a loss of knowledge.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to thank Davood Bahjat Fumani, Philipp Blum, Jorgen Dyrstad, Guy Longworth, Giulia Luvisotto, Elodie Malbois, Martine Nida-Rümelin, Donnchadh O’Conaill, Thomas Raleigh, Chris Ranalli, Johannes Roessler, Mario Schaerli, Gianfranco Soldati and two anonymous referees.

REFERENCES

- Cassam, Q. (2007). Ways of knowing. *Proceedings of the Aristotelian Society*, 107, 339–358.
- Chisholm, R. (1989). *Theory of Knowledge*. Third edition, Englewood Cliffs: Prentice-Hall.
- Coates, A. (2012). Rational Epistemic Akrasia. *American Philosophical Quarterly*, 49, 113–124.
- Conee, E. (2004). Heeding Misleading Evidence. *Philosophical Studies*, 103, 99–120.
- Dretske, F. (1969). *Seeing and Knowing*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.
- French, C. (2012). Does Propositional Seeing entail Propositional Knowledge? *Theoria*, 78, 115–27.
- Ginsborg, H. (2006). Reasons for Belief. *Philosophy and Phenomenological Research*, 72, 286–318.
- Harman, G. (1973). *Thought*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- McDowell, J. (1994). *Mind and World*. London: Harvard University Press.
- McDowell, J. (2002). Responses. In Smith, N., H. (Ed.). *Reading McDowell: On Mind and World*. London: Routledge, 269–305.
- McDowell, J. (2006) Reply to Dancy. In Macdonald, C. and Macdonald, G. (Eds.). *McDowell and his Critics*. Blackwell, 134–142.
- McDowell, J. (2011). *Perception as a Capacity for Knowledge*. Marquette University Press.
- Millar, A. (2011). How Visual Perception Yields Reasons for Belief. *Philosophical Issues*, 21, 332–351.
- Pritchard, D. (2012). *Epistemological Disjunctivism*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Pollock, J. (1986). *Contemporary Theories of Knowledge*. Savage, MD: Rowman and Littlefield.
- Pryor, J. (2000). The Skeptic and the Dogmatist. *Nous*, 34, 517–549.
- Roessler, J. (2009). Perceptual Experience and Perceptual Knowledge. *Mind*, 118, 1013–1041.
- Roessler, J. (2011). Perceptual Attention and the Space of Reasons. In Mole, C., Smithies, D. & Wu, W. (Eds.). *Attention: Philosophical and Psychological Essays*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Stroud, B. (2009). Scepticism and the Senses. *European Journal of Philosophy*, 17, 559–570.
- Sudduth, M. Defeaters in Epistemology. *The Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, ISSN 2161-0002, <http://www.iep.utm.edu/>, accessed 23/01/2017.
- Turri, J. (2010). Does Perceiving Entail Knowing? *Theoria*, 76, 197–206.
- Williamson, T. (2000). *Knowledge and its Limits*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.